

MONAGHAN PILOT, IRELAND

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Monaghan Pilot Region

- A mainly **rural** county in Ireland
 - On the **Border** with the UK (Northern Ireland)
- Rich rolling dairy **grass farmlands**
- Population - 61,386 people – static.
 - 63% in rural areas.
 - 11% new entrants.
- Strong tradition of unique indigenous industry
 - Hub for **innovation** in business & agriculture in Ireland

Monaghan Pilot PoliRural impact & plans

1. Lessons learned
2. Main results achieved
3. Action Plan alignment and adoption
4. Pilot case study
5. Technical tools

Pilot Partners :

mac The National Microelectronics Applications Centre – project management & technical work

Monaghan Integrated Development (MID) – community development company, Monaghan LEADER programme

1. Lessons Learned

● Lessons learned from the project

1. Foresight provides an **innovative & inclusive** approach to rural development
2. However, the process is **complicated** & needs much explanation.
3. **Engaging the stakeholders** is very powerful, but takes a lot of **time, interactions & resources**
4. **New forms of consultation & interaction**, are required especially during a time of **pandemic**.
5. Sourcing the required **data** can be quite a **challenge**

● Recommendations to other Regions with similar needs,

1. Consider using the Foresight - **Go for it !**
2. Use **all** of the Foresight **process steps** as outlined earlier, its worth the effort for the **insights & engagement** of stakeholders to be gained.
3. Give the process adequate **time & resources**.
4. Use a **wide net** when engaging with rural stakeholders - **rural areas are dynamic & complicated !**

Challenges & Learnings in the PoliRural Foresight Process

❑ Challenges

- Engaging **Stakeholders** takes a lot of **time & effort**
- COVID-19 lockdown meant **no user meetings**
- Getting stakeholders to consider **new ideas**
- **Online meeting fatigue**
- PoliRural processes, tools & guides are **complex**, & not immediately **understood** by Stakeholders
- Finding suitable & adequate **data sources**

❑ Lessons Learned

- Pandemic has opened Stakeholders to **change - new ways & ideas**
- Stakeholders engagement takes a **lot of time & effort** - but worth it
- **We**, the local community must **take control of their own rural region's future**
 - Focus on **concrete actions & opportunities**
 - Highlight & promote our region's "**Rural Attractiveness**" especially post-pandemic
 - Use Rural Attractiveness as a **Driver for change**.
 - Find new innovative avenues of **funding**

Changes in how we viewed our region before & now

- **View Before:**
 - **Farming & rural populations are ageing**, & young people are choosing not to farm the land
 - Financial **insecurity** of farming, with overproduction, consolidation & reduced employment.
 - Lack of farming experience/expertise & no support schemes for **new-comers**

- **View Now** : As above + Monaghan is at a **pivotal “Moment of Change”**
 - We, the **local community** can & must **take control of our own future & make our rural region the way we want it to be**
 - Counter-balance Ireland’s over centralised governance & policy making.
 - **locally-orchestrated bottom-up** to meet top-down

2. Main Results Achieved

Multi-stakeholder Collaboration

- **Monaghan Stakeholders Panel** – process core

- Currently 31 members - 61% Male, 39% Female
 - Face-to-face **meetings** pre-COVID
 - Mainly **phone & online interactions** since

- **Broad stakeholders' representation**

- **Direct Participation by the Population of Monaghan**

- 112 attendees, 20 **group** meetings in person & online
- 84 **one-to-one** online interactions in 2 **Deep Dives** - 300 relevant stakeholders targeted
- 10 New Entrants' **Case Studies** + video

➤ **0.3% of Monaghan's** total population of 61,386 have been directly involved so far

New insights & knowledge about our region,

thanks to deep dives, drivers analysis, policy evaluation, policy exploration etc?

- **New Insights:** Monaghan is at a **pivotal “Moment of Change”**
 - EU Green agenda, Brexit, Covid-19, Ukraine war, Climate change => big Challenges & Concerns + emerging **Opportunities** in line with:
 - **EU Long-Term Vision** & policies for rural areas – “Strong, Connected, Resilient & Prosperous”,
 - EU’s green & digital transitions, programmes & funding.
 - Rural Pact & EU Rural Action Plan, new CAP & LEADER, PEACEPLUS.
 - **Ireland’s** CAP Strategic Plan, Rural Development Policy & National Recovery/Resilience Plan & Ireland North-East Regional Enterprise Plan
- Thus **New rules & governance** need to become the “**new norm**” for Ireland
 - Counter-balance Ireland’s over centralised governance & policy making.
 - using the **LEADER methodology - locally-orchestrated bottom-up** to meet top-down

Rural Monaghan's Issues for the Future

Tools that previously didn't exist or were improved

- **Text Mining** – semex.io – extensive easy-scan **Curated Reading List (CRL)** of 729 sources to identify **Issues & Trends**

- **System Dynamic Modelling (SDM)** – Monaghan models' **potential Impact**.

Investment into entrepreneurship and innovation

Population arriving in the pilot area

➤ Intuitive - 👍

AKIS evolution

Indicate evolution over time

Population arriving in the pilot area

➤ Not so Intuitive ➔ Discussion 😊

Digital Innovation Hub / Best Practice Atlas

Monaghan New Entrant Case Studies

RAL The Best Practices Atlas - Polirural

Brenda McGinn – Busy Bee Ceramics
1 Main Street, Glaslough, Co. Monaghan, Ireland

Deanna Campbell (D's Cakes)
Corryrabeg, Carrickroe, Co. Monaghan, Ireland

Jarlath Treanor
Carrickroe, Co. Monaghan, Ireland

LARISSA KLESHNINA
Castleblayney, Co. Monaghan, Ireland

Louise Loughman Artist
Annyalla, Castleblayney, County Monaghan, Ireland

MARK GILLANDERS
Ballinagall, Monaghan, Ireland

Pollocks' Pickles and Preserves
Cornamundy, Monaghan, Co. Monaghan, H18 XW71, Ireland

Sliota Chroi Co-operative Society Ltd.
Aghacloghan, Carrickmacross, Co. Monaghan, Ireland

Subh Fraoic Bán
Drumreask Lodge,

Theresa Kelly of Theresa Kelly Lace

+ Video

How we are influencing change in policies &/or attitudes

- **We are Improving & Finalising the Monaghan Foresight Action Plan** iteratively based on
 - **Stakeholders'** feedback & inputs.
 - Evolving **policies & funding** opportunities
- We are exploring all **suitable avenues of funding** for its implementation
 - from the PoliRural Inventory
- We are Preparing & Progressing **Endorsement & Adoption of the Action Plan**

3. MONAGHAN Action Plan Alignment & Adoption

- **Vision**: By **2030**, Monaghan will be a **strong, connected, resilient & prosperous** rural region, with a vibrant & inclusive community, involving the **highest proportion** of non-traditional **new entrants & young farmers** in Ireland. Where all residents enjoy the same quality of life as all others in the region, with a vibrant rural innovation ecosystem of active rural actors & smart villages.
- **Approach**: The Monaghan Action Plan is focusing on **locally implemented** rural development **policies & initiatives** actively improve the **rural attractiveness** of the region, by addressing Ireland's & **Monaghan's CAP reform & new LEADER plans**

Alignment with LTV4RA: To make our region Stronger, Connected, Resilient & Prosperous

Alignment with LTV4RA:

Monaghan's Action Plan contribution to EU Policy Missions

1. Recovering from the pandemic & improving the resilience of the regions

- Enterprise & Job Creation & leveraging Digitisation
- Rural community Infrastructure, Social Inclusion & Rural Youth
- Sustainable Development of Rural Environment & Climate Change Mitigation

2. Achieving a just transition to net zero by 2050 (the Green Deal)

- Agricultural Diversification & Rural Food Production
- Sustainable Development of the Rural Environment
- Climate Change Mitigation & Capacity Building

3. Implementing a nature-based model of sustainability based on biodiversity

- Sustainable Development of the Rural Environment
- Climate Change Mitigation & Capacity Building

How we intend to facilitate adoption

- **Improve & Finalise the Monaghan Foresight Action Plan** in further iterations based on
 - **Stakeholders'** feedback & inputs.
 - Evolving **policies & funding** opportunities
- Explore all **suitable avenues of funding** for its implementation
 - from the PoliRural Inventory

How we intend to facilitate adoption

- Prepare & Progress successful **Endorsement & Adoption of the Action Plan** by
 - Formally integrating it into the **Monaghan LEADER Programme**
 - also integrating into **MID's long-term Strategic Plan**
- Establish permanent **Monitoring/Governance & progress tracking**
 - Current plan it to continue & enhance the Monaghan Pilot's **Stakeholders Panel** beyond the end of the PoliRural project
 - Data collection & analysis of **annual KPI's**, relating to specific actions listed in this action plan & outputs & an **end-of-LEADER programme evaluation** in 2028 to assess outcomes & impacts.

4. How we intend to use our Pilot Case study

POLIRURAL Compendium of Regional Foresight Initiatives.docx - Google Docs

- How we intend to use our case study from the compendium?
 - Will it be edited?
 - Translated?
 - Published?
 - Disseminated?
- Not yet decided
 - Yes
 - No
 - Probably
 - Yes, beyond the Stakeholders Panel

5. Monaghan Pilot – use of PoliRural Tools

- Current use, as shown earlier ...
- How we intend to use these tools after the project:

Tool	Planned Use
1. Regional SDM	To explore & display possible impact of different Policy Choices, but only by technical specialists , as its complex to use.
2. Semex	To identify issues & trends , but only by technical specialists , as its complex to use.
3. Rural Attractiveness Explorer	To explore Impact of different Policy Choices to Stakeholder Panel using simple diagrams that are clear , new & innovative, which should help us to get attention from policy makers etc
4. Digital Innovation Hub	To help promote the businesses & work of our new entrants
5. Atlas of Best Practices	To help promote the businesses & work of our new entrants .
6. Foresight Action Plan Process inc: Stakeholders involved, Drivers Analysis, Deep Dives, exploring innovative funding, Monitoring/ Governance, progress tracking, etc	To work with our Stakeholders & local community to take control of our own future & make our rural region the way we want it to be . Integrate into MID's long-term Strategic Planning & Monaghan LEADER Programme procedures to counter-balance Ireland's over centralised governance & policy making, i.e. locally-orchestrated bottom-up to meet top-down.

Monaghan – use of PoliRural Guides

- **How we intend to use the PoliRural Guides after the project:**

Tools (Guides)	Planned Use
1. Guide to Deep Dives (Covid)	Possibly repeat it after a period to assess any further trends or changes
2. Guide to Deep Dives (CAP Reform)	Possibly repeat it after a period to assess any further trends or changes
3. Guide to Deep Dives (Green Deal)	To explore its Impact once its better understood by Stakeholders & the new LEADER programme is in place.
4. STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change	Possibly repeat it after a period to assess further trends & changes
5. D1.8 Future Outlooks Methodology	To work with our Stakeholders & local community to take control of our own future & make our rural region the way we want it to be.

Rural Attractiveness Index - Planned use

We plan to use the **simpler RAE** approach at <https://hub.polirural.eu/ra-explorer/#/>

Rural attractiveness index of regions between 2015 and 2040

Rural attractiveness index of regions in 2040.0

Rural attractiveness

2040 Q1

Source: Polirural SDT

“dots” - to get a static image to be included in reports etc

“discs” - to show our evolution over time

“data races” - to show how our ranking changes over time.

Domain Impact Analysis over time

